

Experimental Study of Static Downhole Gas Separators Used in the Orinoco Oil Belt, Venezuela

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ABSTRACT

Downhole gas separators are ubiquitous devices needed for the proper functioning of subsurface pumps. Contrasting its widespread use, the knowledge of its performance is quite limited. In fact, little information is available on literature related to the testing of downhole gas separators with heavy oil. Being able to predict the amount of free gas that will be separated is a key factor for a proper artificial lift equipment selection.

This paper describes the laboratory tests of poor boy and helical separators, both of which are currently being installed in the Orinoco Oil Belt. The poor boy design is perhaps the simplest static separator used in oil production, while the helical separator has a more elaborated design. Tests were carried out using air and ISO 150 (460 mPas at 20.5 °C) mineral oil as working fluids in a large scale experimental facility composed of a 7-inch casing and 3½-inch production tubing. The experimental plan included tests at

80 psig with liquid and gas flow rates between 200 - 500 bpd and 33000 - 236000 scfd respectively.

At testing conditions, the poor boy separator showed a far better separation efficiency than the helical separator. A simple formula for poor boy separation efficiency calculation at the aforementioned experimental conditions is provided. Using these results will allow a more precise pump sizing, especially for oil wells with high gas production and continuous flow downhole pumps such as progressing cavity pumps.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial lift systems based on pumps such as sucker rod, progressing cavity and centrifugal pumps need the attachment of a gas separator at the intake. Gas separators are necessary even for oil wells with low gas production. The function of the separator is to remove as much gas as possible from the gas-oil stream coming from the reservoir.

Avoiding the entrance of said gas is a key factor in order to keep the downhole pump size and running speed within reasonable limits. Now, even with the presence of a gas separator, some gas will succeed in entering the pump and occupying a volume, that otherwise, would have been filled by oil. So, it is useful to know how much gas goes into the separator together with the oil.

In this work, experimental tests of both poor boy and helical separators are presented. The poor boy separator is quite popular in Venezuelan oilfields, used in both sucker rod and progressing cavity pumping systems across all oil viscosities. The use of helical separators is recent and still in evaluation stage on extra-heavy oil wells belonging to the Orinoco Oil Belt (OOB). In the early years, OOB exhibited a very low GOR, so downhole gas separation was not considered an issue. But nowadays, with inroads being made into oil extraction, reservoirs have departed from its pristine initial conditions. Produced gas rates have increased and oil producers regards now downhole gas separation as a key technology for successful OOB operations.

A 3½-inch full size poor boy separator and a 5-inch helical separator in a 7-inch casing were tested at the Artificial Lift Laboratory of PDVSA Intevep. This research addresses the case of a vertical well where the pump intake is placed well above the producing interval. This paper is a continuation of the work initiated by Ibarra et al. [1] where an experimental study of downhole gas separators under viscous flow conditions was presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Oil industry has few publications regarding experimental studies of static downhole gas separator (SDGS) under viscous flow conditions. Most studies have been focused on the characterization of gas separators using low viscosity liquids, usually water.

Lea and Bearden [2] investigated the effect of free gas on the performance of downhole centrifugal pumps. These authors described an “annulus separation effect”, which is essentially the primary separation that takes place in the annular space existing between the production and the pump or separator casings. Two experimental conditions that promoted the separation efficiency were found using water

and air at pressures in the range of 25 to 30 psig: a) the greater the gas volume present and b) the lower overall pumping rate, the greater the separation efficiency.

Podio et al. [3] described a separator based on various improvements with respect to conventional separators: a) decentralized separator, b) placement of inlet ports in the narrower annular region and c) inducing the movement of gas bubbles toward the wider annular region. These improvements can be collectively termed as flow conditioning to get a better primary separation. Podio et al. also defined a “separation capacity”, being the maximum liquid flow rate at which the pump will be filled by liquid almost completely. This is an early indication that there exists a region of high separation efficiency with a defined boundary. Going beyond that boundary will provoke a progressive loss in separation performance.

Robles [4] characterized experimentally the behavior of the most common downhole gas separators using air and oil (3.46 cSt at 25 °C) as test fluids. Robles divided the overall separation process into two stages: a) a first stage taking place at the annular space between the casing and the separator and b) a second stage occurring in the interior of the separator. The first stage was previously identified by Lea and Bearden [2] as the annulus separation effect. In addition to his experimental work, Robles suggested three theoretical aspects related to the viscous effects on gas separation: a) the higher viscosity, the lower the rise velocity for a given bubble size, therefore, a less efficient separation can be expected, b) a higher viscosity reduces the level of turbulence and prevents the breaking of large bubbles which facilitates the separation process and c) flowing viscosity oil through the separator means pressure losses that cause gas liberation in both the separator annulus and through the dip tube.

Lisigurski [5] carried out an extensive laboratory research on various transparent separator models using air and water as working fluids. The experiments showed that liquid superficial velocity inside the separator and gas superficial velocity in the annulus were significant regarding the separation efficiency. Also, Lisigurski found that the lower the static pressure at separator level, the better the separation.

McCoy et al. [6] used the experimental data published by Lisigurski [5]. In their analysis, these authors

pointed out the presence of a “zero gas flow boundary”, where the amount of gas entering the separator was negligible. This boundary was determined by a specific liquid flow rate. The boundary moved to lower values as the gas flow rate increased. The authors performed experiments with different types of separators, signaling that most of the liquid enters the separator through the lower row of openings. Thus, the use of many inlet rows in a separator was discouraged. Finally, the experiments indicated that the gas superficial velocity in the casing–separator annulus modified the separator efficiency.

Bohorquez et al. [7] presented further advances with respect to McCoy et al. [6]’s research. In their work, previous findings such as that entry port geometry does not appear to have a significant impact on the separator efficiency and that there exists a region of low liquid velocity in which the amount of gas that succeeds entering the separator is zero or insignificant were corroborated. These authors also found experimental evidence of the secondary separation stage where some of the gas that was carried inside the separator annulus, flowed upward counter current and was able to escape to the production casing.

Ananaba [8] compared the experimental results and visual observations obtained after changing the dip tube configuration from the conventional straight design to a helical design in static downhole gas separators. The separator designs were tested over a range of 120 - 900 bpd ($0.8 - 6.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) of water and air rates between 13000 and 115000 scfd. The results showed that not only the evaluated static centrifugal separators induced centrifugal forces for gas liquid separation; it also incorporated driving mechanisms that greatly improved overall separation efficiency. Also, the author presented results on laboratory bubble rise experiments on a variety of liquids with different viscosities (1 – 3500 cP) in a vertical wellbore annulus configuration. Ananaba determined that fluid viscosities between 1 and 110 cP decreased the bubble rise velocity in approximately 2 in/sec (about 20% variation). In consequence, the author suggested that results from gas separator experiment using water should be representative of the performance for fluids with viscosities less than 110 cP.

Ramos et al. [9] published the results of static helical separators in Carabobo area of OOB installed in vertical wells. The results obtained from the evaluation were: a) increment

of 45% average production rate per day, b) PCP runlife increase from 12 to 19 months, and c) increase of pumping efficiency up to 25%.

Figuera et al. [10] reported the results of downhole gas separators applications in Ayacucho area of OOB. The models evaluated were static helical, horizontal (inflow V-shaped) and poor boy, installed in vertical, deviated, and horizontal wells. The results obtained from the evaluation of 15 wells were: a) 14% increment in production rate, b) pump runlife increase from 12 to 18 months, and c) increment of pumping efficiency 30% to 40%. Poor boy separators showed the best efficiency with 55%, followed by the horizontal separator which exhibited 35% and finally, the helical separator which yielded 25% efficiency at field conditions (viscosity of foamy oil 2500 cP at 135 °F).

Ibarra et al. [11] presented an experimental study of a poor boy downhole gas separator using air and water as working fluids. Two efficiency regions were identified: a) high efficiency with values in the range of 95% - 98% and b) efficiency depending on gas and liquid flow conditions. The authors corroborated that the main variable affecting the efficiency is liquid flow rate. Gas mass flow rate and gas density are secondary variables, but still influential. The experimental results were condensed into a simple formula to be used in practical cases to estimate the amount of gas that will be ingested by a downhole pump. These findings are restricted to the pumping of low viscosity oils.

EXPERIMENTAL FACILITY

The experimental facility is located at PDVSA Intevep’s Artificial Lift Laboratory. The circuit sketch is shown in Figure 1. The facility has a 7-inch casing where a downhole gas separator connected to a production tubing string can be placed to reproduce the actual geometry inside an oil well. Two-phase flow through this casing is established by a rotary pump and a screw air compressor. The maximum liquid flow rate is about $13 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and it depends on the liquid properties. The air mass flow rate can reach up to 2000 kg/h against a discharge gauge pressure of 700 kPa.

The liquid mass flow rate is measured with a Coriolis flow meter. The air flow rate injected into the circuit can be measured either with an orifice plate or a vortex flowmeter

depending on the amount of gas flow rate. Both fluids merge at a tee junction at the casing bottom. The casing is 20 m tall. The top 8-meter section is made of transparent acrylic tubes. The two-phase mixture travels upward through the casing where it finds the downhole separator under test. At this point, all the liquid and a certain amount of gas flow into the separator through its openings. The remaining gas continues its way up to the free surface and out of the casing. The fluids that enter the separator flow through a 3½-inch production pipe up to the top of the casing. This mixture is discharged into a process separator where air is allowed to escape to the atmosphere while the liquid is sent back to the pump inlet. The flow rate of both exiting air currents are measured with orifice plate meters. The casing hydrostatic pressure is kept stable by means of control valves that regulate the amount of air that is liberated to the atmosphere. The amount of air mass injected is continuously controlled to balance the amount of it that is removed from the circuit. Failure to keep the gas mass balance under check can lead to serious misleading results.

An ISO 150 mineral oil was used as liquid. This fluid has a density of 885 kg/m³ and a dynamic viscosity of 132 mPas at 40 °C. The experimental tests presented in this article were carried out at 550 kPa gauge and 20.5 °C.

GAS SEPARATION TESTS AND DISCUSSION

Poor Boy Separator

Descriptions of poor boy separators can be found in Podio et al. [3], Robles [4], Lisigurski [5], Bohorquez et al. [7], Ibarra et al. [11], Clegg [12], and Campbell and Brimhall [13]. Poor boy separators are simple to build, inexpensive, sturdy and low pressure loss devices, attributes which make them appealing to use downhole. A drawing of the unit tested in this work is shown in Figure 2.

In a poor boy separator, gas removal from the two-phase stream takes place into two clearly distinct stages. Figure 3 depicts the primary separation that happens at the outer face or separator casing, where most of the separation takes place. A fraction of the gas chooses to pass along the separator holes and continues its upward movement through the annular space between the production casing and the separator. The remaining gas is swallowed by the separator

openings due to high local viscous drag. Then, a secondary separation occurs inside the separator. A certain amount of the gas that entered into the separator detaches itself from the liquid pull, escapes through the uppermost row of holes and returns to the annular space. The amount of gas set free is believed to be rather low.

The experimental assembly used can be seen in Figure 4. The poor boy separator was installed with its corresponding dip tube as shown in Figure 4A. The annular section is comprised by the internal casing diameter (158.8 mm) and the external separator diameter (88.9 mm). This annular area has a value of 136 cm².

Each test was defined by the liquid flow rate q_l , total gas mass flow rate \dot{m}_{gt} and gauge pressure at separator inlet p_s . See Table 1 for q_l and \dot{m}_{gt} values. Hydrostatic gauge pressure p_s at the lower separator inlet ports was fixed at 550 kPa. This is the maximum safe pressure for the acrylic section operation. The corresponding air density was 7.8 kg/m³. The average liquid viscosity was 460 mPa s.

Figure 5 shows the gas mass flow rate ingested by the poor boy separator \dot{m}_{gs} vs. q_l for different \dot{m}_{gt} values. As has been shown elsewhere using water and air (Ibarra et al. [11]), the larger the total air mass flow rate, the larger the gas mass enters the separator. In Figure 6 results are expressed in terms of separation efficiency defined as:

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{m}_{gs}}{\dot{m}_{gt}} \quad (1)$$

The large efficiency values obtained are noteworthy. These numbers are comparable to those obtained with water by Ibarra et al. [11], in spite of the larger liquid viscosity. This fact suggests that the combined effect of buoyant forces and reverse flow present in a poor boy separator are stronger than viscous drag to explain the separation performance. It doesn't mean that viscous drag is unimportant, just that it seems to be a lesser player compared to the influence of buoyant forces and reverse flow.

The separation efficiency behavior shown in Figure 6 reveals the existence of a transition zone which depends on liquid flow rate. It can be said that a very high efficiency

region exists when $q_l \leq 2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ where the values of η are 0.98 and higher. In this region, the separation efficiency would be defined as a constant value independent of both liquid flow rate and gas mass flow rate. However, when q_l is higher than $2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, the separation efficiency exhibits a rather linear behavior with negative slope depending on liquid flow increment. Because of the presence of a transition zone, it is safe to state that η for $q_l \leq 2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ is constant, with values close to 98%. In addition, a linear regression model was fitted to the data to represent the separation efficiency for $q_l > 2 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$.

The linear regression model fitting the data in Figure 6 for $q_l > 2 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ is presented in Equation 2:

$$\eta = a_0 + a_1 q_l + a_2 q_l^2 + a_3 \dot{m}_{gt} \quad (2)$$

The a_i coefficients in Equation 2 are: $a_0 = 1.1121411$, $a_1 = -0.0622017$, $a_2 = 0.0045319$, and $a_3 = -9.62 \times 10^{-5}$. The average relative error is 0.56 %.

A plot of η experimental values against the obtained results by Equation 2 is shown in Figure 7. This formula is valid for $2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} < q_l \leq 3.3 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. Equation 2 is for continuous flow, such as happens in a progressing cavity pump. For the case of sucker-rod pumps, it is suggested as an approximation, to use in Equation 2 instantaneous liquid and gas mass flow rates and calculate the average separation efficiency as $\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \eta(t) dt$ where T is the pumping period.

Helical Separator

A sketch of the helical separator is shown in Figure 8 and the experimental assembly in Figure 4B. Notice that a perforated nipple installation in the helical separator assembly is required.

Helical downhole gas separators are meant to remove a certain amount of the gas phase in a tertiary stage. Nevertheless, in this work it was used as a stand-alone device in order to reproduce its current application in OOB.

The helical separator has one large inlet and two outlets. As seen in Figure 8. The first of these outlets

discharges the separated gas into the annular space between production casing and the separator casing. The second outlet conducts the produced fluids to the pump inlet. The key separator component is a helical duct or channel used to transport the gas-liquid mixture from inlet to outlets. The cross sectional shape of the duct may vary. The device tested for this study has a trapezoidal shape like that of Obrejanu's patent [14]. Other shapes are possible. See Obrejanu [15].

The working principle of the helical is to promote gas-liquid segregation by inducing a helical upward trajectory to the mixture of fluids. It is expected that the denser fluid will prefer to travel in the outer region of the channel while the gas or lighter phase will be segregated to the inner wall. The device must provide a long enough developing length to allow for a significant two-phase segregation. When the segregated gas-liquid stream reaches the separator top, the lighter fluid will be exhausted to the annular space and the denser mixture to the pump inlet.

It should be mentioned that it is not evident to the authors of the present article what is the operational envelope of this type of separator. Two questions remain to be answered: a) what is the mass flow rate necessary to achieve a useful degree of segregation? and b) what will prevent the separated gas outlet to invert its role and draw fluids from the annular space?. It must be kept in mind that this outlet is connected unchecked to the pump suction.

During the helical separator tests it was only possible to evaluate the separation performance at \dot{m}_{gt} 48 and 184 kg/h. See Table 1. Unfortunately, higher values of \dot{m}_{gt} were not possible to achieve due to the large amount of non-separated gas that flowed up through the tubing, overflowing the gas mass flow meter capacity.

Figure 9 shows the gas mass flow that enters the separator. The air mass flow increases slightly as the liquid flow rate rises. Said increase is stronger at \dot{m}_{gt} 184 kg/h. This behavior is attributed to the larger gas bubbles population being subject to the liquid flow drag force.

The helical separator efficiency is shown in Figure 10. The efficiency is around 40% at the conditions studied. The larger the liquid flow rate, the smaller the efficiency, although the effect of q_l is rather feeble. On the other hand,

a variation of \dot{m}_{gt} up to 3.8 times doesn't modify the separation efficiency, including q_l larger than $2.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$.

The experimental results don't seem to put in evidence the expected phase segregation effect due to angular movement induced by the internal auger. It is the authors' feeling that most, if not all, of the separation is primary, happening at inlet holes of perforated tube. Also, it is not discarded the possibility that the top gas outlet inverted its flow and behaved as a suction, thus precluding separated gas escapement. Further research would be necessary to clarify this assessment.

Finally, Figure 11 shows the superior performance of the poor boy separator over the helical separator at the experimental conditions tested.

CONCLUSIONS

Two separator designs were evaluated: a) the poor boy, which depends on gravity segregation and reverse flow and b) the helical, which exploits the fluid angular movement to promote phase segregation.

The poor boy separator exhibited a far better performance with efficiency values between 90% and 99%, with an almost linear dependency of liquid flow rate. It is noteworthy the large efficiency values obtained by the poor boy device. These values are comparable to those obtained in previous studies with water, in spite of the larger viscosity. This fact suggests that the combined effect of buoyant forces and reverse flow are stronger than viscous drag to explain the separation performance.

The experimental results from the poor boy separator were condensed into a simple formula. Said formula can be used in practical cases to estimate the amount of gas that will be ingested by a downhole pump. Particularly, when a poor boy separator is installed and it is handling viscous two-phase flow under the average production conditions like those presented in this article.

The separation efficiency of the helical separator turned out to be in the range of 30% to 50%, depending weakly on liquid flow rate. More work is needed, both

theoretical and experimental, to get a solid conclusion about the suitability of helical separators.

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NOMENCLATURE

\dot{m}_{ga} = gas mass flow rate flowing to the annular space.

\dot{m}_{gs} = gas mass flow rate flowing into the separator.

\dot{m}_{gt} = total gas mass flow rate.

p_s = gauge pressure at separator inlet.

q_l = liquid flow rate.

ρ_g = gas density.

a_i = coefficients of regression lineal equation, $i = 0-3$.

η = separation efficiency.

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Figure 1. Circuit sketch for testing downhole gas separators.

Table 1. Experimental plan for poor boy and helical separators.

Separator	Gauge pressure at separator inlet (kPa)	Gas density (kg/m ³)	Total gas mass flow rate (kg/h)				Liquid flow rate (m ³ /h)	Liquid viscosity at 20.5 °C (mPa s)
Poor boy	550	7.8	47	198	295	340	1.3	460
Helical			48	184	-	-	2.6	
							3.3	

Figure 2. 3 1/2-inch poor boy gas separator.

Figure 3. Downhole gas separation sketch.

Figure 4. Experimental assembly. Poor boy separator (A). Helical separator (B)

Figure 5. Gas mass flow rate ingested by poor boy separator vs. liquid flow rate.

Figure 6. Poor boy separation efficiency vs. liquid flow rate.

Figure 7. Plot of experimental values of η vs. fitted values with Equation 2 with +/-2% bounds.

Figure 8. Helical separator sketch.

Figure 9. Gas mass flow rate ingested by helical separator.

Figure 10. Helical separation efficiency vs. liquid flow rate.

Figure 11. Separation efficiency comparison between poor boy and helical devices.